

ON THE LEVEL OF SHOOT READINESS OF LAW ENFORCEMENT OFFICERS AND PROBLEMS OF FINDING THEIR ACCEPTABLE SOLUTIONS

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Abstract: The article describes the problematic issues of shooting training of law enforcement officers and suggests ways to solve them that are acceptable from a scientific point of view based on the analysis of the rational organization of the process of pedagogical influence in combat shooting.

Keywords: weapon use algorithm, optimality, shooting training, shooting skills, formation of stable shooting skills.

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Currently, it is difficult to imagine the educational process without innovations and active teaching methods. It is no exaggeration to say that this also applies to the science of shooting training of experts. At the same time, ongoing research shows that even the newest practical technologies and ideas do not always lead to expected results [1]. Objectively, this is explained by the fact that any innovation, no matter how modern, cannot be accepted as a concept. At the same time, a new idea (hypothesis) can be considered as an auxiliary didactic method. Observations show that any narrow field, including the most famous and innovative technical or other solutions, is used as a methodological aid in conducting lessons. To a greater extent, this situation is explained by the use of special training complexes (MTM) today. At the same time, teachers and instructors should know that if the students have not mastered the proper holding of the weapon in the staff, skillfully pressing the trigger, aiming, the purpose of the actions performed, etc. without basic skills, in our opinion, the use of special training sets by itself does not affect the result. Specialists (instructors) confirm that such special training sets significantly help in finding and eliminating deficiencies in the shooter's actions, studying and presenting their cause-and-effect results. This can also be achieved when the teacher uses various separate-constructive methods in the initial period, and then holistic constructive methods, taking into account his creative and meaningful approaches to the educational process. But it should be remembered that no special training complex can be considered a training method.

Thus, the experience of practical activity, including participation in training events, competitions and competitions, made it possible to present the process of

working with weapons and performing a set of prescribed training, accompaniment and final actions in their combat use.

On the basis of a visual image of the process of using a weapon, it is possible to study the features of the pedagogical effect to develop the level of shooting training among law enforcement officers and to distinguish the most complex elements. As a rule, many actions to improve (imbibe) relevant skills should be performed as a set of operations resulting from the introduction of various elements into one structure one by one or as a single operation. At the same time, it is recommended to combine such actions with the method of performing one after the other. In addition, the features of the formation of shooting skills include negative physiological manifestations expressed in the form of the shooter's defensive reactions to the events inherent in the shooting process - this is a strong noise effect from the sound of the shot, the physical effect of the recoil forces and the muzzle of the weapon. A dazzling effect behind the cut.

In addition, the use of weapons in various conditions of the specific characteristics of law enforcement activities also implies the formation of a set of mental and logical actions. These actions are aimed at: assessing the situation and the legality of the use of weapons; choosing the most optimal position for shooting depending on the terrain, camouflage possibilities, natural shelters and visibility of the target; choosing an appropriate shooting position based on the circumstances of the situation (standing, lying down, kneeling, etc.); determine the distance to the target to set the target and select the target point; making the necessary corrections during shooting to take into account the movement of the target; choose the type of fire and adjust it.

Among other factors, the following significantly affect the stability of shooting skills:

long-term lack of practice in the use of weapons, actions with weapons that ensure the effectiveness of shooting leads to the loss of automation skills;

stress factors, these are factors that cause uncertainty, anxiety, anxiety and other negative situations in shooting, and negatively affect the effective use of skills and competencies formed during working and using weapons, which have increased to the level of automaticity;

external factors (weather conditions, level of light and noise, level of physical activity, compliance of equipment, weapons with normal combat requirements);

understand the learner's personal interest in improving individual transition training skills and the need to conform to the model of a military serviceman capable of confidently using the weapon assigned to him in defense of the country and its citizens.

Effective shooting skills include a set of techniques developed independently and in parallel. All elements of these abilities are interrelated, but the main link in the whole chain is the act of aiming consciously. Changes in the formation of these special skills cannot be considered a primary phenomenon, since the changes in the methods of kicking and holding the breath are a consequence of the violation of the act of aiming. A conscious approach to mastering shooting skills and abilities is formed as a result of knowing one's actions. It is recommended to use video recordings of the student's actions and their results in the process of teaching accurate hitting of objects and targets. By visually showing video recordings of activities and explanations, learners were shown how they progressed from lesson to lesson. The cadets identified the positive and negative factors of their shooting, studied their mistakes in depth, and received appropriate guidance on the direction of self-improvement. It is recommended to focus on the mind in the acquisition of skills, and the acquisition of visual-motor coordination is crucial [2].

It should be noted that during the research, the issues of instilling the skills of accurate occupation of objects and targets from automatic weapons, including on foot (on the road), were also studied. The main goal was to reveal the process of formation of the skills and abilities of aiming the weapon at the target while shooting on the move and the skill of holding the weapon during automatic shooting. At the same time, special attention was paid to the formation of visual-motor connections that allow the cadets to give the correct direction to the weapon when shooting from automatic weapons. Using the method of holding the weapon by pressing it on the shooter's body, the effectiveness of automatic firing was achieved without stopping the movement and giving the required direction to the aiming device [3].

Faculty and instructors should consider that non-target shooting training may involve cadets firing specially colored bullets at white shields. Each learner can observe the corresponding colored holes on the shield and make corrections in the next training session. In the course of such training, future specialists form visual-motor connections between the central axis of the weapon's direction and the target. In the absence of such training, the formed practical skills are lost, and their recovery requires training with a high consumption of ammunition. In addition, the increase in the accuracy of shooting from automatic weapons (in Russian - *kuchnost*) was experimentally confirmed by the method of holding the weapon during automatic fire [4].

In conclusion, it should be noted that the specific characteristics and conditions of the use of weapons in the formation of stable shooting skills determine the search, testing and application of relevant innovations in the training process.

REFERENCES:

1. Arunov M.P. On new methods of conducting training sessions in combat shooting. - M., 2015. - Page. 58-68.
2. Kosymov V.V. Improving the content of fire training. / Chirchik VTKIU, 2015. - Page. 28-44.
3. Foreign methods of teaching shooting from small arms [Electronic resource]. URL: [http://www.klimvd.ru/files/Raboti%20nauchnie/Petrovich Zelenin Postnikov.pdf](http://www.klimvd.ru/files/Raboti%20nauchnie/Petrovich_Zelenin_Postnikov.pdf) (accessed 01/30/2023).
4. Sarkisov S.N. Modern methods of teaching fire training for the purpose of high-quality performance of operational and service tasks. - T .: Publication of the Academy of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan. - 2018. - Page. 13-26.